

Synthesis of novel multicomponent refractory alloys consisting of Mo, Nb, Ta and W

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Abstract

Multicomponent alloys consisting of four or more elements are being studied extensively and this is currently an active field of materials research. Since the discovery of the equiatomic FeCrMnNiCo alloy in the '70s by the research group of Cantor [1], literally hundreds of compositions have been studied [2]. The interest in these systems is not just in advancing our knowledge of materials, but also from the viewpoint of practical applications, since many multicomponent systems have been shown to possess outstanding mechanical properties, resistance to corrosion, etc. Several of these alloys have also been observed to have high configurational entropy

This presentation discusses the synthesis of refractory alloys containing Mo, Nb, Ta and W for use in demanding environments. Since these metals melt at high temperatures, it is difficult to synthesize them using conventional methods such as solid state reaction. We have adopted a microwave-assisted process, wherein the formation of the alloy and its consolidation are expected to take place simultaneously. Since the mechanism of heating materials in microwaves is different as compared to other techniques, the kinetics of formation are also different. Results from preliminary experiments will be presented and a comparison with other methods will also be made.

Keywords: multicomponent alloys, high entropy, microwave-assisted synthesis

References:

1. Cantor et al., Mater. Sci. Engg. A 375-377, 213
2. Murthy, Yeh and Ranganathan, "High entropy alloys", Butterworth Heinemann publications (2014) London.